

Linguistics and its methods

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Аннотация: В статье анализируются языкознание и методы его изучения, язык и культура являются основой изучения данной области, а также взгляды ученых на методологию языкознания.

Annotation: The article analyzes linguistics and its study methods, language and culture are the basis of study of the field and the views of scientists about the methodology of linguistics.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, язык, культура, методология, лингвокультурологические методы.

Key words: linguistic and cultural studies, language, culture, methodology, linguocultural methods.

Today, when globalization and intermingling of cultures are taking place, the interaction of language and culture, that is, the field of linguo-cultural studies, is widely studied and analyzed. It is known that language is a mirror of culture, because it reflects the worldview, thinking, traditions and national character of a whole nation. That is why linguists describe language as a "mirror of culture", "treasure of culture", "carrier of culture", "weapon of culture". In linguistics, the science of linguoculturology was formed as a field that studies the commonality of language and culture.

Studying the relationship between language, culture, ethnicity is an interdisciplinary problem. The solution to this problem can be solved only with the joint efforts of several disciplines, from philosophy and sociology to ethnolinguistics and linguistics. For example, linguistic philosophy with ethnic issues of linguistic thinking, psycholinguistics with specific linguistic aspects of ethnic, social or group communication, etc. is engaged in. Linguistics as an independent branch of linguistics emerged in the 90s of the 20th century ¹.

Linguistics studies myths, legends, other examples of folk oral creativity, or simple dialogue texts recorded from the folk language, or in the phraseological layer of the language, which have acquired a symbolic, figurative, metaphorical meaning in the culture, and the results of which are generalized in the human mind, imagined through the visual world. language units that appear are listed. It is also known that the emergence of a linguistic and cultural unity can be the result of the desired national traditions turning into phraseology, proverbs or matals.

¹ Телия В. Н. Русская фразеология семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологический аспекты. –М: Школа “Языки русской культуры”, 1996. –С. 286.

Linguistics is a science that studies the human, or rather, the cultural factor in a person. This means that the center of linguistic and cultural studies is a complex of achievements characteristic of the anthropological paradigm of man as a cultural phenomenon².

Linguistics is focused on the human factor, more precisely, on the cultural factor in a person. The fact that the center of linguistic and cultural studies consists of the phenomenon of culture indicates that it is a phenomenon related to the anthropological paradigm of man³.

So, linguistics studies live communicative processes - the use of language expressions related to the culture and mentality of the people, that is, their consciousness, popular traditions, and customs. So, linguaculturology is one of the new directions of linguistics that studies the interaction of language and culture, and like all departments, it deals with the analysis of the language of works through its own methods.

Methodology is the application of worldview principles to the cognitive process. Methodology as a general theory of methods came into the world with the need to generalize the methods used in human cognitive activity. Since the dialectical method is a teaching that affects special scientific methods, that is, methods related to various disciplines, it was called methodology, that is, a teaching about methods that are a method of scientific research. Initially, methodological problems were seen within the framework of philosophy⁴.

A complete methodology has not yet been formed in the direction of modern linguo-cultural studies, and scientists associate its methodology with the methodology of linguistics. The main task of linguistic and cultural methods is to study the relationship between language and culture more fully and more clearly through analyzes and examples. As the methods of linguistic and cultural science, methods and directions related to language and culture are used in fields such as culturology, linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and anthropology. Because linguistic and cultural studies is the field that embodies their research. That is why several methods of cultural studies and linguistics are selectively used in the process of linguistic and cultural analysis.

Any specific method of scientific research has its limitations. However, the interacting language and culture are so multifaceted that it is impossible to know

² Телия В. Н. Русская фразеология семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологический аспекты. –М: Школа “Языки русской культуры”, 1996. –С. 222.

³ Слишкин Г. Г. От текста к символу. Лингвокультурные концепты прецедентных текстов в сознании дискурса. –М: Academia, 2000.- 128 с.

⁴ Usmonova яS. Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik. –Т.: Bookmany print, 2022. –В. 40.

their nature, functions and genesis by means of one method. Therefore, it is quite natural to use a number of complementary methods in this field ⁵.

Linguistic, culturological, sociological, ethnographic methods can be mentioned among the methods of linguistic and cultural studies. These methods complement each other in the process of cultural analysis and serve to increase and facilitate the research methods of language and culture relations, which have a complex relationship in linguistics and culture. Many scientists have opinions about the division of this field into methods. In particular, the linguist Lakoff proposes the method of analyzing metaphors to study the interaction between language and culture.

Another famous linguist, Telia, puts forward the idea of using the macrocomponent method as a convenient method of linguistic and cultural studies. In this case, cultural analysis is carried out step by step. Some scientists also propose a method of researching the relationship between language and culture through texts regarding the methods of linguo-cultural studies.

Modern linguistic and cultural studies methodologically relies on three foundations: 1) V. von Humboldt and A. A. Potebnya's teaching; 2) to the hypothesis of the multiplicity of worlds; 3) to the hypothesis of linguistic relativity. As a more serious methodological basis, the teaching of V. von Humboldt and A. A. Potebnya, who raised the issue of interaction between language and culture, is relied upon. However, in today's process of globalization and integration, this doctrine is considered outdated and disconnected from living life. Therefore, the main task of modern linguistic and cultural studies is to go beyond the scope of linguistics, to describe the living processes of language and culture, and most importantly, to scientifically predict the development of language and culture ⁶.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the main task of linguistics is to analyze the interaction between language and culture through convenient and understandable methods and to show that it is a large field separate from linguistics, which is to identify the aspects of our culture that are mixed with our language through its methods. implemented and developed through.

References:

1. Телия В. Н. Русская фразеология семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологический аспекты. –М: Школа “Языки русской культуры”, 1996.

⁵ Маслова В. А. Лингвокультурология. Учеб. Пособие для студ. Вьестю учеб, заведений. –М. Издательский центр “Академия”, 2001. –С.35.

⁶ Usmonova S. Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik. –Т.: Bookmany print, 2022. –В. 43.

2. Слишкин Г. Г. От текста к символу. Лингвокультурные концепты прецедентных текстов в сознании дискурса. –М: Academia, 2000.- 128 с.
3. Usmonova S. Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik. –Т.: Bookmany print, 2022. –В. 40.
4. Маслова В. А. Лингвокультурология. Учеб. Пособие для студ. Вьестю учеб, заведений. –М. Издательский уентр “Академия” ,2001. –С.35.

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